

8T and Einstein Relativity

O Manor

June 6, 2021

Abstract:

The following is an analysis of the relativity idea by the new framework, 8T. The analysis will done via the main equation and the coupling constant equation in the first and second representations, i.e. net variations and spin. Using that framework, it becomes vividly clear that the existence of two observers, which differ in the amount of curvature they create, and the same measured object, will eventually measure different times and distances. The reason is the following: their innate difference causes the metric to accelerate in different amounts. So relativity is very simple in this framework, all it takes is two different observers and the same measured object. Reader is assumed to have read the thesis of the 8T, as little to no explanation will be made concerning the equations presented in this paper.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Define an observer, distinct observer, as an arbitrary amount of curvature on the manifold. An infinite series of fermions.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$N \rightarrow \infty \quad (3.1)$$

Define an additional observer, distinct, which differ in the amount of curvature it creates on the metric. The observer is an infinite series of fermions which overall vanish into matter.

$$\sum_{r=1}^M \delta g_r = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

$$M \rightarrow \infty \cap M! = N \quad (3.3)$$

Now, analysis of the two observers on equation (1.2). Assume they are measuring the same object, and the entire metric is null, the entire metric contain each observer and the measured object. The setting chosen for simplicity sake, as those things will be too complex to analyze in a real physical scenario. Defined the measured object for both observers as:

$$\sum_{k=1}^T \delta g_k = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

Now for the first observer and the measured object, the total arbitrary variation summed as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{k=1}^T \delta g_k = 0 \quad (4)$$

Now for the second observer and the measured object, the total arbitrary variation summed as:

$$\sum_{r=1}^M \delta g_r + \sum_{k=1}^T \delta g_k = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{k=1}^T \delta g_k \neq \sum_{r=1}^M \delta g_r + \sum_{k=1}^T \delta g_k \quad (6)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_{ik} - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g'_{ik} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_{rk} - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g'_{rk} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Those observers will cause the matrix to accelerate outward so the object will be observed moving. His velocity is dependent upon the amount of curvature the observer is creating, and so two different observers, different by the above definition, will measure two different distances crossed and two different times for the same object. The reason however, is not for the object itself, it's the different nature of the observers, and in particular the amount of curvature they possess. Now since we proved the yang mills conjecture we have the same propagation speed for all bosons:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &8 + (1) \\
 &[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \\
 &[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \\
 &[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \\
 &[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \\
 &[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \\
 &[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

The time needed to cross the same matrix which accelerated outward in different amounts is different. So, measured time which is different for each observers is quite vivid and a must by using (1.2) and the 8T framework. In fact, using such framework makes relativity notoriously complicated, as everything needs to be taken into account. Everything is causing the matrix to vary; it is at a verge of impossible to do at the real world. Our best theories are radically simplified. By "everything", one means every arbitrary variations of fermion in the matrix needs to be taken into account, which was not done in that analysis for simplicity sake. The majority of the paper was known to the reader. What is different is the reason of relativity and the analysis of this beautiful idea in the 8T framework, which imposes additional complications, in quantum scale.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)